

Style Guide: Human Reference Atlas 2D Functional Tissue Unit (FTU) Illustrations

Preface

This guide is intended to catalog a shared set of design standards, updated at regular intervals to reflect our current understanding of the purpose each type of 2D functional tissue unit (FTU) illustration will serve. The success of the Human Reference Atlas (HRA) effort depends upon massive contributions of data, in conjunction with contributions from many subject matter experts and research teams.

Anticipated 2D illustration needs include:

- An interactive educational tool for use on the Common Coordinate Framework (CCF) portal.
 - Illustrations must be linked to relevant anatomical structures and cell types present in the ASCT+B (Anatomical Structures, Cell Types, and Biomarkers) table for the relevant organ via a crosswalk table. Crosswalk tables contain information from the .svg illustration file which links the illustration to the ASCT+B table and allows for user interactivity which highlights structures on mouseover.
- Images that work (either at the sketch stage or as final illustrations) to help train AI algorithms in better recognizing cell types and anatomical structures.

Design Considerations and Constraints:

- Developing a standard illustration style that will be particular to the HuBMAP project, but easily adaptable and shared with others for open source educational uses.
- The illustrations should be clear enough to visually separate anatomical structures and/or cell types, depending on the scale of each FTU.
- Also important are the number of total cells and number of cells in each FTU, and the total number of cells by cell type.
- A consistent visual explanation of scale should be applied to each 2D illustration, along with the HuBMAP icon.
- Special care should be taken to consider accessibility of the project, including ease of conversion of color to a grayscale or black and white palette, inclusion of alt text elements, and considerations for colorblind users.

We propose to solve these issues and set forth a clear style guide for application to future HuBMAP illustrations and graphics for publication across print and digital media.

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Typography

Inter Regular

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMm
NnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
0123456789

Inter Bold

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMm
NnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
0123456789

Type Size

Title - 14

Example The quick brown fox
jumps over the lazy dog.

Sub head copy - 11

Example The quick brown fox jumps
over the lazy dog.

Body copy - 9

Example The quick brown fox jumps
over the lazy dog.

Palette - Graphs and Charts

R: 106 G: 111 B: 131 light #696e83	R: 130 G: 130 B: 130 light #828282	R: 225 G: 92 B: 161 light #e15ca1	R: 219 G: 118 B: 93 light #db765d	R: 95 G: 154 B: 218 light #5f9ada	R: 137 G: 160 B: 95 light #89a05f
R: 68 G: 74 B: 101 main #44a65	R: 99 G: 99 B: 99 main #636363	R: 218 G: 52 B: 138 main #da348a	R: 210 G: 84 B: 53 main #d25435	R: 55 G: 129 B: 209 main #3781d1	R: 108 G: 137 B: 56 main #6c8938
R: 47 G: 51 B: 70 dark #2f3343	R: 69 G: 69 B: 69 dark #454545	R: 152 G: 36 B: 96 dark #982460	R: 147 G: 58 B: 37 dark #933a25	R: 38 G: 90 B: 146 dark #265a92	R: 75 G: 95 B: 39 dark #4b5f27

Palette - Illustration

R: 247 G: 227 B: 216 light #f7e3d8	R: 170 G: 121 B: 104 dark #aa7968	R: 216 G: 130 B: 152 main #d88298	R: 236 G: 210 B: 232 light #ecd2e8	R: 122 G: 80 B: 151 dark #7a5097	R: 157 G: 198 B: 157 main #9dc69d
R: 250 G: 217 B: 193 main #fad9c1	R: 249 G: 199 B: 220 light #f9c7dc	R: 224 G: 107 B: 132 dark #e06b84	R: 157 G: 117 B: 179 main #9d75b3	R: 189 G: 211 B: 180 light #bdd3b4	R: 0 G: 104 B: 55 dark #006837

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Color illustration (Primary Illustration Choice)

- Anatomical structures and cell types are differentiated by palette choices, with attention given to choosing high contrast values to separate cellular components and neighboring tissue types when possible.
- Dark gray outlines (# 4d4d4d) are used when graphically separating functional tissue units (FTUs) and to define visual borders.
- Consideration should be given as to how much context (surrounding anatomy) to include when illustrating FTUs.

Leader line style:

- 0.5 pt black stroke over 0.5 pt white stroke
- First word capitalization
- Lines may be angled as necessary, with a preference for using 90 and 45 degree lines where possible

_____ Sample label

Grayscale/black and white illustration

- Apply high contrast values when working in color and check the translation to a black and white palette.
- Check color blind filters in Adobe Illustrator's press preview when preparing graphics for print.

Scale Bars

- Scale bars should be included to add a scale reference for any cellular-level illustrations.
- Line weight is 1.5 px, and label text is 16 pt Inter Regular font.
- [Use this link](#) to access an Adobe Illustrator version of a standard scale bar and icon lockup.

Scale bars and HRA icon

Human Reference Atlas (HRA) Icon

- The HRA icon (red blood cell with a white "H" in the center) is displayed on every 2D illustration.
- If scale bars are included, the icon should be on the right-hand side of the scale bars.

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2D FTU Illustration Overview

The following slide is an overview of the first 10 FTU illustrations created. They have been organized according to size, and each category relates to a corresponding scale bar below.

[Follow this link](#) to access a pdf of these 10 2D FTU illustrations including labeling and insets.

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Small-scale FTU Illustrations

- Each of these FTUs has been illustrated at the cellular level and colored by cell type. Anatomical structures may be implied but are not differentiated at this scale. Colors are selected to highlight divisions between cell types, and color choice is used to emphasize these divisions.
- Blood supply is visible in each FTU, and red blood cells are incorporated for reference.
- Organic cell shapes and natural variation is included.
- Cellular structures such as microvilli, pedicels, and goblet cell secretions are visible on the individual 2D illustrations.

Medium-scale FTU Illustrations

- At this scale, we have removed color variation, individual cell boundaries and most outlines. Here we are emphasizing the total number of cells visible in an average FTU, and the general layout and organization of those cells. Anatomical structures are not specifically included but may be implied by the organization and shape of cell nuclei.
- Insets were created for each medium-scale FTU which include all the relevant cell types and anatomical structures included in the ASCT+B table (see lobule of liver at right.)

Large-scale FTU Illustrations

- Currently, the nephron tubule is the outlier at this scale, and only anatomical structures (not cell types) are visible. These have been differentiated using color, similar to the style for small-scale FTUs.
- Insets were created showing cross-sections of these anatomical structures at the cellular level (see full layout at right.)

For more information on the technical process of creating these illustrations at all resolutions, please see ["SOP: Creating 2D Illustrations for Functional Tissue Units."](#)

